

Magnetic Resonance Imaging in Evaluation and Characterization of Sellar and Juxtaseilar Lesions with Histopathological Correlation

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ABSTRACT

Background: The wide spectrum of sellar and juxtaseilar lesions often present with similar symptoms demonstrating profound neuroendocrine manifestations. Preoperative noninvasive diagnosis with magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is essential for treatment planning. Thus this study intended to assess the accuracy of Magnetic Resonance Imaging in imaging of sellar and juxtaseilar lesions taking histopathological findings as gold standard.

Methods: This cross sectional observational study was carried out during January 2023 to September 2023. Total 66 patients who were clinically suspected having sellar/juxtaseilar lesions were included in the present study and underwent MRI examination. MRI was performed in GE Sigma Architect 64 Channel 3T MRI Machine.

Results: Out of 66 patients, 51.5% cases were males and 48.5 % cases were females. Most common pathology was adenoma (54.5%) followed by Craniopharyngioma (18.1%) and meningioma (10.6%). Histopathological correlation revealed MRI accuracy of 93.94%, 93.91%, 100%, 96.97%, 98.48% and 98.48% for the diagnosis of adenoma, craniopharyngioma, meningioma, pilocytic astrocytoma, apoplexy and epidermoid respectively.

Conclusion: The present study revealed a strong correlation between MRI and histopathological diagnosis for sellar and juxtaseilar lesions. MRI is the modality of choice for characterizing sellar and suprasellar lesions.

Keywords: MRI, Magnetic resonance imaging, Macroadenoma, Craniopharyngioma Meningioma.

INTRODUCTION

The sella turcica and adjoining area is a small but complex component of the central nervous system, containing many vital structures. The wide spectrum of sellar and juxtaseilar lesions often present with similar symptoms demonstrating profound neuroendocrine manifestations. Early diagnosis and accurate characterization are able to provide significant clinical benefit. While definitive diagnoses usually await histologic correlation, a systematic approach and knowledge of the key anatomy and imaging features can help in narrowing down the differential diagnosis and sometimes to reach a specific one.¹

At least 30 different lesions occur in or around the pituitary gland, arising from either the pituitary gland itself or the structures that surround it.² Pituitary tumors account for up to 15% of all intracranial masses, and at least 75-80% of all sellar/juxtaseilar masses are due to one of the "Big Five": Adenoma (most common), meningioma, aneurysm, craniopharyngioma, and astrocytoma. Clinically active pituitary adenomas occur at a prevalence of 1:1064 to 1:1288 to the general population. Other sellar lesions include nonneoplastic cystic lesions, germ cell tumors, gliomas, lymphomas, meningiomas, metastatic tumors, vascular lesions, granulomatous and inflammatory lesions, and infections including bacterial abscesses as well as pituitary hyperplasia.³

Magnetic resonance imaging has virtually supplanted other imaging techniques such as CT as the modality of choice for evaluation of the sellar and juxtaseilar regions. Its major advantages are its superior soft tissue contrast and capacity for multiplanar imaging.⁴ Dynamic MR Imaging plays a very important role in the evaluation of pituitary adenomas, particularly in accurate delineation of those microadenomas with no contour abnormality, to assess invasion by macroadenoma and in post-operative evaluation in cases of residual / recurrent lesions.

In India, the prevalence in Rajasthan was 7.6%. Unfortunately, no nationwide prevalence and incidence data is available from Indian cohort.⁵ However, there is a dire need for country-specific research to formulate patient treatment and management guidelines. A multi-disciplinary approach involving endocrinologist, neurosurgeon, Radiologist, histopathologist etc. would be very helpful.

Thus this study is intended to assess the accuracy of Magnetic Resonance Imaging in imaging of sellar and juxtaseilar lesions taking histopathological findings as gold standard.

METHODS

This cross sectional observational study was carried out during January 2023 to September 2023 in the department of Radiodiagnosis, S.M.S. Medical College and Hospitals, Jaipur. Total 66 patients who were clinically suspected having sellar/juxtaseilar lesions were

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included in the present study and underwent MRI examination. Claustrophobic patients and patients with general contraindications to MRI such as pacemakers, metallic fixations, etc. were excluded from the study. The procedure was communicated to the patients and the informed consent was taken in written format. A brief history and examination was done at the time of MRI scan. MRI was performed in GE Sigma Architect 64 Channel 3T MRI Machine. Different MRI features in terms of T1W and T2W signal characteristics (iso/hypo/hyperintensity), consistency, enhancement, and involvement of adjacent structures were noted in the structured format. The consistency of different lesions was categorized into solid, cystic, Solid - Cystic and Cystic with Mural nodule. The diagnostic accuracy of MRI in assessing sellar/juxtaseilar lesions was compared with histopathological finding taken as gold standard.

RESULTS

The findings of the Sixty-six patients were compiled and analyzed. Out of 66 patients, 51.5 % cases were males and 48.5 % cases were females. Maximum number of cases were in the age group of 31-40 years (28.8%), followed by patients in the 51-60 years age group (19.6%). Over 50 per cent cases (~57.5 %) were in 11 to 40 years age group. Youngest patient was 4 years old and oldest patient was 71 years old,

Table- 1 shows the clinical feature of the patients with sellar lesion.

Most common symptoms observed were headache (62%) and diminution of vision (51.5 %). These both were together observed in 37.8 per cent cases.

Table 1 – Distribution of respondent according to clinical feature:

Clinical Feature	No. of Cases	Percentage
Headache	43	62
Diminution of vision	34	51.5
Combined (headache & diminution of vision)	25	37.8
Acromegaly	4	6
Cushing syndrome	4	6
Infertility/erectile dysfunction/decreased libido/Menstrual irregularities	4	6
Others – vomiting/ limb weakness/ seizures/ polyurea/polydipsia	8	12

Among all the Sellar, suprasellar and para-sellar lesions, 50 per cent cases showed elevated pituitary hormones level and 3.1 per cent decreased level whereas 46.9 per cent cases showed normal level.

Majority of pathologies in sellar and juxtaseilar regions were neoplastic (~89%).

Most common pathology was adenoma (54.5 %) followed by Craniopharyngioma (18.1%) and meningioma (10.6 %). Except one pathology (two microadenomas were seen in a single patient), all other pathologies had single lesion. Over 85 per cent pathologies (~87.5 %) had well defined margins. Further, approximately 90% pathologies had both suprasellar and sellar components. [Table 2]

Table 2 – Distribution Of Pathologies in Sellar and Juxta-Sellar Regions

Pathology	No. of cases	Percentage
Adenoma	36	54.5
Craniopharyngioma	12	18.1
Meningioma	7	10.6
Pilocytic Astrocytoma	3	4.5
Pituitary Apoplexy	2	3
Epidermoid Cyst	2	3
Rathke Cleft Cyst	1	1.5
Tuberculoma	1	1.5
Lymphocytic Hypophysitis	1	1.5
Enchondroma	1	1.5
Total	66	100

Majority of pituitary adenomas were macroadenomas (88.8%). Among macroadenomas, ~37.5 % were giant macroadenomas (> larger than 4 cm in at least one dimension). The second most common tumor was craniopharyngioma, most of the cases were children (75 %) and among them majority of were in 5 to 15 years age group (50 %). Youngest and oldest patients were of 4 and 51 years of ages respectively. No case was seen in 20 to 30 years and above 60 years age groups. All of the meningioma cases were in adult age group, youngest patient was of 37 years age and oldest 61 years.

All of the adenoma showed contrast enhancement, ~58 % heterogeneously enhancing and ~42 % homogeneously enhancing. Similarly, all craniopharyngioma and meningioma showed contrast enhancement, where most of craniopharyngioma manifested as rim/nodular enhancement (~83%) and 71% meningioma showed homogeneous enhancement followed by heterogeneous and rim enhancement.

Out of 66 Sellar/Juxta sellar lesions, ~56 % were isointense on T1W images followed by ~28 % hypointense and rest ~16 % hyperintense. Majority of adenoma (~66%) and meningioma (~85%) were isointense and Craniopharyngioma (~41%) were hyperintense on T1W images. Whereas, Most of adenoma (~66%) and Craniopharyngioma (~91%) were hyperintense and ~71 % meningioma was isointense. None of the Adenoma, Craniopharyngioma and meningioma were hypo, iso and hyperintense on T2W respectively. Most of the adenoma cases (75%) and meningioma cases (85.71%) were solid in consistency, whereas 41.67% of craniopharyngioma cases were mixed solid-cystic in consistency. [Table 3]

In our study, high concordance percentage was observed for Meningioma (100%), Adenoma (94.7%), Craniopharyngioma (85.7%) and Rathke Cleft Cyst (100%), moderate for Apoplexy (66%) and Epidermoid (50%) and low for Pilocytic Astrocytoma (33%), lymphocytic Hypophysitis, Tuberculoma & Enchondroma. [figure 1]

Figure 1 – Concordant Percentage Between MRI Diagnosis & Histopathology

Out of total 38 cases of MRI diagnosis of Adenoma, 3 turned out to be another pathologies – Tuberculoma, Enchondroma and Lymphocytic Hypophysitis. Further one case of MRI diagnosis of nasopharyngeal SOL came out as Adenoma. Whereas, out of total 14 cases of MRI diagnosis of Craniopharyngioma, 3 turned out to be another pathology- two Pilocytic Astrocytoma and one Epidermoid Cyst. Further one case of MRI diagnosis of Pituitary Apoplexy came out as Craniopharyngioma. All of the Meningioma cases were diagnosed correctly on MRI and there was no false negative case leading to 100 % - sensitivity, specificity, PPV, NPV and accuracy parameters. There was only one case of Rathke Cleft cyst which was diagnosed correctly. None of the Lymphocytic Hypophysitis, Tuberculoma or Enchondroma cases were diagnosed correctly on imaging. [Table 3]

Table 3 - Accuracy Parameters of MRI in Diagnosing Major Sellar/Juxta-Sellar Pathologies Taking Histopathology as Gold Standard

Pathology	Sensitivity	Specificity	Positive Predictive Value	Negative Predictive Value	Accuracy
Adenoma	97.22	90	92.11	96.43	93.94
Craniopharyngioma	91.67	94.44	78.57	98.08	93.91
Meningioma	100	100	100	100	100
Pilocytic Astrocytoma	33.33	100	100	96.92	96.97
Apoplexy	100	98.44	66.67	100	98.48
Epidermoid	50	100	100	98.46	98.48

All values are in %.

DISCUSSION

Diagnosing Sellar and Juxta-Sellar pathologies can be quite complex. The Sellar region, located in the central

skull base, houses the pituitary gland and is surrounded by critical structures such as the optic chiasm, cavernous sinuses, and carotid arteries. This intricate anatomy makes imaging and interpretation challenging.

Clinical profile, lesion morphology, signal intensity on various sequences, and contrast enhancement pattern are taken into consideration when characterizing masses with MRI; however, even if the data are evaluated together, there can still be difficulties in the differentiation of various Sellar and Juxta-Sellar pathologies. The major aim of this study was to describe MR imaging characteristics of the lesions of the Sellar and Juxta-Sellar region; to correlate the MRI findings with histopathological findings and to assess the diagnostic accuracy of MRI in characterization of these lesions.

The patients belonged to all age groups ranging from 4 to 71 years in our study. However, Maximum number of cases were in the age group of 31-40 years (28.8%), followed by patients in the 51-60year age group (19.6%), 21-30year age group (15.1 %) and 11-20year age group (13.6%).

Our results are consistent with the study conducted by Dogar T et al⁶, Banna et⁷ al, Goyani BR et al⁸, Prerit J et al⁹, Batra V et al¹⁰, Karthikeyan V et al¹¹, Omprakash et al¹², Pratisruti Hui et al¹³ and Kaushal B et¹⁴, who also encountered maximum number of patients in these age groups. There was slight male preponderance (male-female ratio - 1.06:1) in our study which was similar to Karthikeyan V et al¹¹ and Omprakash et al¹² experiences; in contrast to Banna et al⁷, Kaushal et al¹⁴, Batra V et al¹⁰, Pratisruti Hui et al¹³, Suman et al¹⁵ and Prerit J et al⁹ who reported a female preponderance.

Headache (62%), followed by visual disturbances (51.5 %) and combined (headache and visual disturbance) (31.5%) were the most common symptoms in our study, and other complaints were hormonal imbalance leading to amenorrhea, galactorrhea, infertility, erectile dysfunction, Cushing syndrome and acromegaly and mass effect causing seizures, hemiparesis, and vomiting, these findings are similar to the study done by Karthikeyan V et al¹¹, Pratisruti Hui et al¹³ and Batra et al¹⁰. This particular involvement of symptoms is explained by the fact that most of the Sellar lesion have suprasellar extensions which causes mass effect leading to raised intracranial pressure so headache and compression and elevation of optic chiasm so visual disturbances.

Our study observed that pituitary adenomas, craniopharyngioma, and meningioma were the major constituents for the study consisting of 54.5%, 18.1%, and 10.6% of the cases, respectively, followed by pilocytic astrocytoma (4.5%), epidermoid (3%), and apoplexy (3%). There was one case of each lymphocytic hypophysitis, tuberculoma, rathke cleft cyst and enchondroma.

These findings are similar to what was observed by Johnsen et al³, Batra V et al¹⁰, Omprakash et al¹², Pratisruti

Hui et al¹³, Karthikeyan V et al¹¹, Kaushal B et al¹⁴, Hemalatha et al¹⁶, Batra V et al¹⁰ and Prerit J et al⁹ who all observed that the most common lesion in Sellar and Juxta-Sellar region was adenoma followed by craniopharyngioma and meningioma. Majority of pathologies in sellar and juxtaseellar regions were neoplastic (~89%) in our study consistent with other above-mentioned studies.

Pituitary Adenoma

In the present study, there were 36 pituitary adenoma cases which constituted about 54.5% of total pathologies in Sellar and Juxta-Sellar regions. Maximum number of cases were in the age group of 31-40 years (41.6 %). Out of 36 adenomas 32 were macroadenomas and 4 were microadenomas by size criterion. The proportion of macro to microadenoma was 8:1. Johnsen et al found the total proportion of macro to microadenomas 2.5:1 while Kaushal B et al observed it to be 10.5:1. Though literature says that microadenomas are more common than macroadenoma in general population.

High signal intensity on T1W images may be seen due to presence of hemorrhage in macroadenoma. We found that 24 cases (66 %) of macroadenomas were isointense to grey matter, 8 (22%) were hypointense and 4 (12%) were hyperintense on T1W images, and on T2W images 24 cases (66.6%) of macroadenomas were hyperintense to grey matter, 12 (33.3%) were isointense and none was hypointense.

Our findings of enhancement pattern of macroadenoma were similar to findings observed by Johansen et al³ and Kaushal B et al¹⁴. The presence of cystic/necrotic/haemorrhagic areas were reasons for heterogeneous enhancement. In our study in about 37.5% of the cases, internal carotid artery (ICA) encasement is noted which is supported by Johnsen et al³ and Pratisruti Hui et al¹³ where it was 43% and 42% respectively.

Our diagnostic accuracy parameters (sensitivity, specificity, PPV, NPV & accuracy - ~97%, 90%, 92%, 96% & 94%) are similar to what were observed by Kaushal B et al¹⁴, Batra V et al¹⁰.

Craniopharyngioma

Majority of the craniopharyngioma cases have peak age of occurrence at 5–15 years, followed by a small peak in 45–60 years' age group, and have equal sex distribution supporting our findings. In the present study having total 12 Craniopharyngioma cases, most of were children (75 %) and among them majority of were in 5 to 15 years age group (50%). Male-female ratio was 1: 1, therefore no gender predilection was noted in our study. On T1W images 5 cases (41%) of macroadenomas were hyperintense to grey matter, 4 (34%) were hypointense and 3 (25%) were isointense. Whereas, on T2W images all except one hypointense case were hyperintense; similar to what was shown by, Batra V et al¹⁰ and Suman et al¹⁵. Our data were correlated with the study by Pratisruti Hui et al¹³ where they also didn't find any completely solid

Craniopharyngioma case and most common consistency was solid-cystic. All of the cases showed enhancement, most common pattern was peripheral rim/nodular enhancement followed by heterogeneous enhancement. These observations are consistent with the findings observed by Kaushal B et al¹⁴.

Out of total 14 cases of MRI diagnosis of Craniopharyngioma, 3 turned out to be another pathology-two Pilocytic Astrocytoma and one Epidermoid Cyst. Further one case of MRI diagnosis of Pituitary Apoplexy came out as Craniopharyngioma. Our diagnostic accuracy parameters (sensitivity, specificity, PPV, NPV & accuracy - ~92%, 94%,78%,98%&94%) are similar to what were observed by Kaushal B et al¹⁴, Batra V et al¹⁰.

Meningioma

Meningiomas in Sellar region may arise from tuberculum sellae, diaphragmatic sellae, clinoid processes, optic nerve sheaths and wings of sphenoid. There were seven histopathologically proven meningiomas in our study. male-female ratio was 0.4:1 which was supported by Johnson et al³, Kaushal B et al¹⁴.

Meningiomas typically show iso-intensity on T1- and T2-weighted sequences with characteristic homogeneous enhancement. In our study, all showed iso-intensity on T1W; on T2W 71 % were isointense and rest hyperintense. All of meningioma cases showed enhancement; 71 per cent as homogeneous enhancement and rest as heterogeneous enhancement and all were solid in consistency Similar findings were observed in Batra V et al¹⁰, Hemalatha et al¹⁶ and Suman et al¹⁵.

All of our meningioma cases were diagnosed correctly on MRI and had 100% concordance rate with histopathology so our diagnostic accuracy parameters stand as (sensitivity, specificity, PPV, NPV & accuracy – 100% for all). Similar results were observed by Pratisruti Hui et al¹³ and Suman et al¹⁵. Hemalatha et al¹⁶ recorded 90% sensitivity and 100% NPV in diagnosis of meningioma in her study.

CONCLUSION

MR imaging demonstrated distinct characteristics that enabled effective differentiation among various sellar and juxtaseellar pathologies. The diagnostic accuracy of MRI for pituitary adenomas and sellar region tumors was strongly validated by histopathological correlation, showing high sensitivity and specificity. Hence, MRI can be considered as the modality of choice for diagnosing sellar and suprasellar, lesions with high accuracy, sensitivity, and specificity.

Abbreviations

CT: Computed Tomography
ICA: Internal Carotid Artery
MRI: Magnetic Resonance Imaging
NPV: Negative Predictive Values
PPV: Positive Predictive Values

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Availability of data and materials

Data will be available by emailing deepak2011meena@gmail.com

Authors' Contributions

- Author1: Literature search, conceptualization, methodology, data acquisition, manuscript preparation and editing.
- Author2: Conceptualization, supervision, validation, review and editing.
- Author3*: Writing, reviewing and editing.
- Author4: Data collection.
- Author5: Data analysis and interpretation.

All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript. All authors have read the final manuscript.

Ethics approval and consent to participate

The research adhered to the ethical principles outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki (2013). Approval for the study protocol was granted by the S.M.S. Medical College and Attached Hospitals, Jaipur Ethics Committee, with a decision number of 421 in 2023. Electronic signatures were obtained as informed consent from all individual participants involved in the study. Every procedure conducted during the study complied with the standards of S.M.S. Medical College and Attached Hospitals, Jaipur Ethics Committee and aligned with the principles set forth in the 1964 Helsinki Declaration, along with its subsequent amendments.

Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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